

RADNEXT Transnational Access Summary Report

Project title	<i>Heavy Ion test beam with Demonstrator ASIC for Radiation-Tolerant Transmitter in 28 nm CMOS</i>
Project TA identifier	<i>TA08-211</i>
General application	<i>High Energy Physics</i>
Type of test	<i>SEE</i>
Group leader, Institute	<i>Paulo Moreira / Szymon Kulis, CERN</i>
Author list	<i>S. Biereigel, M. Baszczyk, P. Moreira, F. Martina, A. Klekotko, S. Kulis, P. Moreira</i>
Date(s) of the experiment	<i>12 December 2024</i>
Facility	<i>RADIation Effects Facility, University of Jyvaskyla</i>
Amount of access granted	<i>8h</i>

Objectives of the experiments

The DART28NRZ ASIC, developed at CERN within the Strategic R&D Programme on Technologies for Future Experiments [1], is designed to demonstrate high-speed Non-Return-to-Zero (NRZ) data transmission at 25.6 Gbps under extreme radiation conditions, as expected in future high-energy physics environments. The ASIC features four identical channels, each comprising a Data Pattern Generator, a Forward Error Correction (FEC) encoder, a high-speed serializer, an All-Digital Phase Locked Loop (ADPLL), and a Dual-Use Driver (DUDE) [2] configurable for transmission-lines or Ring-Modulators.

The primary objectives of the experiment include studying the DART28NRZ chip's response to ionizing particles, focusing on Single Event Effects (SEEs), and assessing the circuit-level countermeasures for SEEs. Additionally, the experiment aims to evaluate the effectiveness of a novel technique to compensate for Single Event Transients (SETs) in LC oscillators, assess the effectiveness of the full Triple Modular Redundancy (TMR) technique for SEE mitigation, and evaluate the proposed FEC/interleaving schemes for SEE mitigation.

The experimental work plan involves exposing the chip to heavy ions with the highest Linear Energy Transfer (LET) (above 30 MeV/(mg/cm²)) to identify all SEE signatures, measure the limit cross section, and aim to exclude sensitivity to Single Event Latch-up (SEL). Additionally, an ion scan will be performed with LET in the range of 1-20 MeV/(mg/cm²) to enable a reliable fit of the sensitivity curve for Single Event Upsets (SEU) using a Weibull function.

The choice of beam and specific test vehicles is motivated by the need to replicate the extreme radiation conditions that the DART28NRZ ASIC will face in future high-energy physics experiments.

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The heavy ion beam was chosen to thoroughly test the chip's resilience to intense ionizing radiation and to ensure that any potential vulnerabilities, such as SEL, are identified and mitigated. The ion scan with various LETs is selected to provide a detailed sensitivity curve for SEE, which is critical for extrapolating the error rates in anticipated radiation environments.

Experiment test report

Figure 1: Schematic of the experimental setup.

The dedicated test bench setup, schematically presented in Figure 1 and described in detail in [3], was designed to facilitate a thorough evaluation of the DART28 chip. Central to this setup was the DART28 chip itself, wire-bonded to a custom test PCB, ensuring electrical connections and optimal signal integrity. An FPGA board was employed for both communication and control purposes, allowing for seamless interfacing with the DART28 chip. To handle high-speed data transmission, Intel QSFP transceivers were utilized, converting the electrical signals from the DART28 into optical signals that were transmitted via fibre optics to a receiver on the FPGA side. Additionally, an HPTC board was incorporated to provide a low-jitter reference clock. The setup also included a software-defined radio (SDR)-based phase measurement system [4], which enabled accurate monitoring of the clock output. To continuously monitor the DART28 chip's power consumption onboard voltage and current monitoring integrated circuits (ICs) were employed.

The chip's SEE immunity was tested by exposing it to heavy ions at the RADEF facility in Finland. This

exposure allowed for a detailed assessment of the chip's performance and reliability under ionizing radiation. The campaign aimed to characterize the SEE of the DART28 ASIC, focusing on the I²C interface, configuration memory, clock generator, serializer, and output driver radiation response. It also sought to evaluate data transmission and link performance under radiation, as well as to detect any latch-ups. A photograph of test board installed on the beam line is presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Photograph of the experimental setup.

The ASIC configuration during the tests was optimized to ensure error-free data transmission without beam, focusing on a single active channel operating at 25.6 Gb/s. Utilizing DART framing with a 10-bit header and 560-bit user payload (PRBS7), the configuration bypassed scramblers and interleavers to maintain required data run lengths and mitigate power delivery network (PDN) issues discovered during the initial prototype evaluation. Four configurations were tested, including both unprotected and TMR-protected modes operations for the data path and serializer.

Throughout the entire experiment, no sudden increase in power supply current, indicative of a latch-up event, was observed.

The configuration interface and memory of the DART28 ASIC demonstrated robust performance throughout the testing period, with no instances of corruption observed in the configuration memory. Utilization of the SEU correction counter effectively extracted flip-flop cross-section data, aligning well with anticipated behaviour reported in the community. The I²C interface operated reliably without disruptions during testing. However, a limited number of 'hard resets' of the ASIC were observed, prompting an investigation that pinpointed a likely cause in an IO cell supplied by the foundry. The hypothesis will be confirmed through future laser testing. This issue was successfully mitigated during the campaign by reconfiguring the ASIC after each event to promptly restore link functionality without significant loss of beam time.

Figure 3: Phase transients measured with gear shifting or the TDC phase detection enabled.

The clock generator's performance is pivotal for ensuring error-free data transmission, with the PLL playing a critical role. No severe single-event effects (SEE) affecting the clock generator were detected, but approximately 100k soft SEEs occurred, primarily due to the inherent sensitivity of an inductor within the oscillator [4,5]. Despite these SEEs, the PLL exhibits graceful recovery, experiencing only brief phase errors before stabilizing. The built-in time-to-digital converter (TDC) combined with the SEE detection mechanism effectively minimizes peak phase errors, ensuring that phase deviations do not lead to bit errors, particularly when the detection mechanism is active.

The effectiveness of the proposed mitigation strategy is demonstrated in Figure 3, which shows the phase deviation with the feature enabled and disabled. As illustrated, the feature significantly limits the peak phase deviation and shortens the recovery time. A histogram of peak phase errors is presented in Figure 4.

Figure 4: ADPLL phase transient cross-sections measured with gear shifting or the TDC phase detection.

A few step-like phase jumps were observed ranging from 40 to 50 ps each. These occurred exclusively at the highest LET of 60 MeV·cm²/mg and resulted in a 1-bit shift of the frame in the FPGA receiver, leading to temporary loss of frame synchronization followed by automatic resynchronization by the FPGA. The likely cause was attributed to hits on the oscillator feedback amplifier. However, the impact was deemed minimal or negligible as such LET values are highly improbable in our typical operating environments.

Excluding the events related to resets and PLL issues previously discussed, the link was found to be highly reliable with no other functional interruptions or loss of synchronization observed. Over a 5-hour period of beam time, during which 4×10^{14} bits were transmitted, only approximately 10^3 bit-errors occurred.

Figure 5 shows the experimentally obtained cross-section for the circuit, both with TMR protection enabled and disabled. The data demonstrates a significant improvement achieved using the implemented TMR strategy, reducing the limit cross section by at least an order of magnitude and substantially increasing the upset threshold LET. The cross-section of the TMR-protected circuit does not reduce to zero because ions still can generate SETs in the majority voter placed at the serializer output or in the DUDE resulting in data corruption. The obtained cross-section values align with the physical circuit area of the DUDE. Moreover, during both measurements, the interleaving feature was bypassed (due to the PDN limitation), significantly reducing the effectiveness of the FEC encoding.

Figure 5: Bit error cross section as a function of the LET with fitted Weibull curve for protected and non-TMR protected circuit. For TMR protected circuit, no errors for the lowest LET ion have been observed [6].

The SEE data with the TMR enabled has been used to analyse SEE inside DUDE. The TMR protection of the data path and serializer mitigates any bit upsets originating in these circuits, leaving only the driver sensitive to SEE. The longest observed SET inside the driver had a length of 7 bits, being equivalent to 274 ps. This was observed only for the most energetic ion, while for the $^{83}\text{Kr}^{29+}$ the length of the burst was halved, and for the $^{20}\text{Ne}^{7+}$, no errors were observed. Nonetheless, all of these error bursts are shorter than the correction capability of the employed FEC. Therefore, in normal operation with the interleaver enabled, it is expected that they can be corrected, ensuring error-free data transmission.

References:

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Outcome of the experiments

Please indicate what the experiment is likely to lead to by putting an 'X' next to one or more of the possible outcomes below.

Journal publication	x
Data for Thesis	x
Follow-up experiment at same facility	
Follow-up experiment at another facility	x
Other	

As a RADNEXT user, we encourage you to submit the scientific results of your experiments to journals as well as to the NSREC and RADECS data workshops. Please remember to include the RADNEXT acknowledgment into your publications!

RADNEXT acknowledgment:

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101008126.